

Cognitive Peculiarities of the Concept “Friendship”

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Abstract:

This article deals with the origins of the notion of concept, along with the detailed analysis of the linguistic literature on methods of describing the concept. In this work, it is proposed a comprehensive phased cognitive-conceptual analysis, in which, depending on the purpose of the study used the principles of conceptual analysis, based on the preparation of a cognitive map, on the construction of the concept of nominative fields and cognitive interpretation of metaphor.

Keywords: notion of concept, cognitive nature, cognitive map, frame, friendship

INTRODUCTION.

The notion of the concept began to be formed and is widely used in linguistic studies since the mid XX century. One of the first linguists, who have studied the concept, was C.A. Askoldov. In his article «The concept and the word» published in 1928, the researcher treats the concept as a «mental entity that replaces us in the process of thought vague set of objects of the same kind of» [1].

In this regard, the key point in the cognitive nature of the concept serves as vice-monetary function. It should be noted that the term “concept” was used as a synonym for the concept. In our view, is synonymous with the use of two terms due to interlingua lexical equivalence of these two words. Translated from the Latin concept’s meaning idea, the notion of «semantic meaning of the name (sign), i.e. the content of the concept, the volume of which is the object (denotation) of the name».

The identification of the terms of the concept and the concept is illustrated by the Grand-agency encyclopedia Dictionary of linguistics: «The concept - the phenomenon of the same order as the meaning of the word, but is not considered a somewhat different system of linkages, value - in the language system, the concept - a system of logical relations and forms, as studied in linguistics, and a logic».

This definition supports the idea that the concept of nature in terms of new approaches to language learning is different from the meaning of the word and is interdisciplinary in nature, and this, in turn, serves as one of the main provisions contemporary linguistic research. In this regard, the concept has a broader meaning than the concept, and established as an independent and a key term in the studies on the problems of cognitive linguistics, cultural linguistics, psycholinguistics, philosophy of language, communicative linguistics, pragmatic linguistics, i.e., all the linguistic areas, based on the interdisciplinary nature of language learning. However, the identification of the concept and the concept is not excluded, as some scholars consider these terms as synonyms.

MATERIALS REVIEW

The term «concept» is traced back to 1554–60 (Latin *conceptum* - «something conceived») but what is today termed «the Cognitive linguistics, is the process of producing and transforming concepts (meanings), so the most important object of research in cognitive linguistics is a concept. Concepts, speaking as components of our consciousness and our knowledge of the world are studied in philosophy, psychology, cognitive linguistics, cultural linguistics and other humanities. Exploring the nature of the concept in cognitive linguistics is paramount. Any attempt to understand the nature of the concept leads to awareness of the existence of a number of related concepts and terms. First of all, this is a concept, a notion and meaning.

Firstly, a concept (abstract term: conception) is a cognitive unit of meaning an abstract idea or a mental symbol sometimes defined as a «unit of knowledge,» built from other units which act as a concept's characteristics. A concept is typically associated with a corresponding representation in a language or symbology such as a single meaning of a term. There are prevailing theories in contemporary philosophy which attempt to explain the nature of concepts. The representational theory of mind proposes that concepts are mental representations, while the semantic theory of concepts (originating with Frege's distinction between concept and object) holds that they are abstract objects. Ideas are taken to be concepts, although abstract concepts do not necessarily appear to the mind as images as some ideas do. Many philosophers consider concepts to be a fundamental ontological category of being. The meaning of «concept» is explored in mainstream information science, cognitive science, metaphysics, and philosophy of mind.

In cognitive linguistics, abstract concepts are transformations of concrete concepts derived from embodied experience. The mechanism of transformation is structural mapping, in which properties of two or more source domains are selectively mapped onto a blended space. [2]

The development of methods for studying the concept is today one of the topical problems of modern linguistics. American linguists define concept as a unit of thinking. [3] Conceived as a complex education and consciousness unit, representing the linguistic means and forms a semantic space of language, which is studied by means of specially developed methods in linguistics. Research concepts aimed at «interpretation of the meaning structures, objectifying certain features of concepts; to identify the frequency (typical of many concepts) taxonomic characteristics and the definition of the characteristics common to these typological traits studied concepts. Then - based on them - a generalization of the concepts of features, as well as the selection of conceptual structures and cognitive models of language schemes actualization concepts studied in compared languages»

Currently, the development of methods of conceptual analysis involves the study of the interaction of human cognition with linguistic structures, has accumulated some experience. This issue has received considerable attention in the work of linguists such as N.D.Arutyunova, E.S.Kubryakova, Stepanov, R.M.Frumkin, M.V.Pimenov, Z.D.Popova, I.A.Sternin, V.I.Karasik.

The origins of conceptual analysis are incorporated in the frame of the theory proposed by M.Minsky. The method is based on the position that the human perception of reality is carried out by comparing its existing frames in the memory, the data structures associated with the conceptual objects that are stored in the memory and are necessary to represent a stereotyped situation. Under the frame is defined as «a unit of knowledge organized around some concepts, but in contrast to associations containing the data on the material, typical and possible for this concept» differing conventional nature, they concretize, which is typical of a certain culture.

The hierarchical structure of the frame is made up of top-level name of the frame, and the lower level consisting of terminals or slots sites that contain specific information on the mentioned frame, and can have their subslots / subframes. Slots describe the subject of the research reveal the specifics of its use. Subframes interframe define relationships between different conceptual objects, stored in the memory. Thus, the frame consists of a plurality of slots that are filled with words, joined by other frames, so new slots, the study of the relationship which gives the opportunity to present what can and cannot happen in the future, i.e., It provides information on the typical frame of action and follow-up. Through frames, which are «packages of knowledge» [4] or information that exist in memory, cognitive interpretation made standard situations, which implies adequate linkages between conceptual objects in memory. To frame the analysis is primarily determined by the language means designating studied conceptual object as a complex structure, or frame, in particular language carriers. Then identifies key terminals/slots which form a frame structure, associative connections are established, activating these slots, i.e., modeled conceptual field of each slot. When comparing multiple languages identified as universal and national-specific elements of the content of the frame in each of the languages being compared.

As a result, frame analysis becomes possible structuring concepts of frame that exists in the minds of speakers of a language, and identifying similarities and distinctive features in the perception of the studied frame members matched linguocultures.

Further development of the conceptual analysis, frame-based method, was in the concept E.S.Kubryakova, which proposed a method for constructing a cognitive map. The cognitive map is based on the lexicographical definitions of words, associative links, characteristics of speech, the most common contexts. Lexicographic presentation conducted on the basis of definitions of smart, phraseological, etymological dictionaries, as well as data dictionaries of synonyms.

Associated components are identified with the help of associative dictionaries and thesauruses. Most important in the interpretation of the concept have a different kind of knowledge structure derived from encyclopedic, mythological, historical, philosophical and cultural sources. One of the most important stages of the concept of research methodology is a reference to the most common contexts of use of the word-concept. For these purposes are analyzed logical unit, in particular, proverbs, and aphoristic texts, quotes, sayings. The final stage of the proposed method is to appeal to the various genres of artistic text, which largely determines the human knowledge of the world, as conceptual analysis.

E.S.Kubryakova believes that «conceptual analysis involves finding common concepts, which are summed up under one sign and determine the existence of a sign as a cognitive structure that provides knowledge about the world. Based on the definition of the concept, it is possible to build a «cognitive map» of the word, is, firstly, a reflection of the most common contexts of the word, and secondly, a statement of all the areas in which are the transformation of word semantics, and finally, a recommendation to the complete lexicographic representation meanings of the word «. The methodology of conceptual analysis, the proposed E.S.Kubryakova, based on a full, three-dimensional analysis of the semantics of the word which, being in the center of the diagram, it is «generating mechanism, the source of its diverse» sweeps «and makes it possible to provide further tap on the points in this diagram»[5]

Along with the semantic analysis of the words used in this methodology contextual analysis, which contributes greatly to the field of conceptual explication of the concept under consideration. In the proposed methodology interact and complement each other component-semantic and contextual analysis, resulting in cognitive map gives an idea of the words of a variety of semantic

relations, reflecting the ratio of the individual meanings of the word and integrate them into a coherent whole. Thus, the method based on drawing cognitive maps, cognitive reveals the essence of the word-concept and allows you to simulate the deep semantics, the internal shape of the studied concept.

The most complete description of the method of conceptual analysis obtained in Z.D.Popova, I.A.Sternin, which marked the main stages of the analysis of the concept, based on the semantic-cognitive method. According to this procedure, the concept analysis is carried out as follows:

- 1) describes the macrostructure of the concept, ie, It is the distribution of cognitive symptoms in the figurative, information components and interpretive field and establish their relationship on brightness / predominance in the structure of the concept;
- 2) describes the concept of categorical structure, i.e., It is «the identification of the hierarchy of cognitive classifications, conceptualizes corresponding object or phenomenon, and a description of the concept of a hierarchy of cognitive classifications»;
- 3) describes the field organization identified cognitive symptoms, i.e., set core proximal and extreme periphery on the basis of cognitive signs and symptoms of cognitive content is represented as a field structure.

The methodology of conceptual analysis play an important role in cognitive interpretation of metaphor, which, as noted by K.Iriskhanova, acts not only as a stylistic technique, but also as a means of conceptualizing. In terms of this approach, the metaphor is seen as a cognitive or cultural model, which is understood as «a stereotypical image, by which organized the experience», «concepts that are used to structure the experience and understanding of the world» [6] «tools at the same time internal and external, social and cognitive». According to K. Iriskhanova, cultural model of stylistic reception also corresponds to these parameters, which explains the «dual nature of stylistic techniques that exist in the form of the scheme, and then implemented in the text, which is formed in the flow integrable individual versatile concepts», due to the ontological (mental) and epistemic (cognitive) nature of metaphors. Thus, metaphor is defined as «basic mental operation as a way of learning, categorization, conceptualization, evaluation and explanation of the world».

The cognitive approach to the study of metaphor brilliantly represented in the work of John Lakoff and M. Johnson «Metaphors we live by», which developed the theory that «metaphor brought consistency in the description of a cognitive mechanism and demonstrated great heuristic potential applications of the theory in a practical study». «According to the authors, «a metaphor pervades our everyday lives and is manifested not only in language but also in thought and action, i.e. person expresses thoughts are not only metaphors, but metaphors and thinks, because «Our everyday conceptual system in which we think and act, is essentially metaphorical».

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The results of metaphorical thinking are concepts verbalized by cognitive metaphors or, in the terminology of John Lakoff and M.Johnson metaphorical concepts that are found in the deepest foundations of human conceptual systems are «fixed assets conceptual framework with which we perceive the objects of one type in terms of objects of a different type, reflection means a more well-known, usually a particular sphere. The metaphor is based on the interaction between the sphere of the source and the target area in which the system of knowledge structures (frames, concepts) the conceptual scope of the source are the basis for modeling the conceptual scope of

the target. The source of knowledge that make up the conceptual sphere, is spiritual, cultural, social, linguistic experience of human interaction with the surrounding reality. The cognitive metaphors, according to George Lakoff, so deeply rooted in the human mind, which is often not recognized as a metaphor, as «It is an integral part of the cultural language media paradigm», and «the most fundamental cultural values consistent with the metaphorical structure of the basic concepts of the culture». [7]

Cognitive metaphor in our work determine the content of the concept shaped component, which plays an important concept of the structure, in some cases, the dominant role. In this regard, interest is proposed by Z.D.Popova, I.A.Sternin research methodology shaped the component. These researchers have isolated shaped component of the concept of perceptual and cognitive images. Perceptive image reflects sensory representations that are generated using human senses and include the visual, audible, tactile, olfactory and gustatory images. Cognitive image is represented by semantic and metaphorical concept ties with other concepts, i.e., cognitive metaphor, which is based on personalization and personalizing the name of the concept on the basis of inherent human - moral, emotional evaluation, intellectual, its cultural skills, reflecting the characteristics of metaphorical denotation of the concept. [8]

For the purpose of our work a detailed analysis of the linguistic literature on methods of describing the concept justified by the need to develop its own methodology, methods and techniques of analysis that contribute to the most adequate description of Friendship/Do'stlik/Дружество.

In this study, we propose a comprehensive phased cognitive-conceptual analysis, in which, depending on the purpose of the study used the principles of conceptual analysis, based on the preparation of a cognitive map by E.S.Cubreacov, on the construction of the concept of nominative fields by Z.D.Popova, I.A.Sternin and cognitive interpretation of metaphor by George Lakoff and M. Johnson, who we believe are complementary and provide an integrated, comprehensive approach to the concept of cognitive analysis. In addition, examination of the structures of knowledge embedded in the language units, verbalized this concept implies an interdisciplinary approach, taking into account the structure of knowledge of different disciplines: philosophy, psychology, theology, culture, aesthetics, history and so on.

It should be noted that our proposed integrated, incremental analysis we conduct based on several principles:

- A. structural principle, involving cognitive signs distribution conceptual, imaginative and valuable components;
- B. the principle of the field, which helps to establish the hierarchy of cognitive-conceptual signs related to the core or the periphery of the structure of the concept;
- C. cross-layer principle, involving consideration of linguistic resources, verbalized this concept at the level of vocabulary, word formation, phraseology units paremeological, aphoristic, artistic, journalistic and sacred texts;
- D. comparison of the principle of contributing to the establishment and allomorphic isomorphic cognitive-conceptual features of the concept under consideration in order to identify its cultural identity.

The test procedure involves several stages:

- Revealed a set of linguistic resources on the lexical level, word formation, phraseology, paremiological units, aphoristic, artistic, journalistic and sacred texts, the study verbalized concept in each of the languages in question;
- Set a hierarchical system of cognitive-conceptual signs by constructing cognitive maps based on the lexicographical definitions of associative connections, encyclopedic knowledge structures, philosophical, cultural character of each of the above levels of verbalization of the concept under study;
- Carried out the interpretation of the cognitive-conceptual signs on a) field-principle; ascribed to the core or periphery at every level of verbalization of the concept; b) structural principle; belonging to the conceptual, figurative and value components of the concept of structure;
- Analyzes the conceptual signs based on lexicographical interpretation keyword-representatives their word formation and phraseological bonds which, depending on the level in question constitute the core or the periphery of the structure of the concept;
- Identifies the cognitive-conceptual signs based on metaphorical nominations forming shaped component of the concept of structure at every level of verbalization of the concept under study;
- An analysis of the value component of the concept of the structure reveals the cognitive-conceptual signs that determine the importance of the concept being studied for the carriers studied linguocultures. The analysis is performed at each level of verbalization Friendship/Do'stlik/Дружество;
- Held an interlayer, comparative and cross-cultural analysis of linguistic units of English, Uzbek and Russian languages that represent the analyzed concept. The purpose of this analysis is to identify the cultural identity cognitive and conceptual features of the concept of structure in each of the languages in question;
- Set the interaction concept Friendship/Do'stlik/Дружество with other concepts that make up the conceptual sphere of the test concept are identified and interpreted them correlative cognitive-conceptual signs to facilitate the identification of conceptual space throughout concept spheres;
- Identifies the cognitive-conceptual signs, forming a religious picture of the world in each of the considered linguocultures.

Conclusion

To sum up, this work is based on the linguistic perception of concept. It differs from other views, because concept is related to a certain way of its expression in language. [9] Concept is an ideal content, any thinking unit, having the meaning, [10] a complex thinking image, operational thinking unit verbalized by different means of speech in the process of communication. [11]

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